

Indian Journal of Politics and International Relations

IJPAIR

Indian Journal of Politics and International Relations

Vol. 16 No. 1 2023

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Indian Journal of Politics and International Relations

Vol. 16 No. 1

2023

Interstate Migrant Workers and Healthcare System in Kerala, India: Critical Examination of Social and Institutional Inclusiveness

*Indian Journal of Politics
and International Relations*
ISSN 0973-5011
Vol. 16 No. 1 2023
3-18

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Abstract

Kerala is the first state in India to introduce social security and welfare schemes for migrant workers in India (Srivastava 2020). The security schemes and welfare schemes announced by the Central Government are being implemented in Kerala in an exemplary manner (IMN Report 2020). Various important tasks pertaining to the healthcare of interstate migrant workers have been showing substantial improvements related to various aspects of inclusion timely delivery of services as well as improved access to the system. This was especially visible during the time of COVID-19, which has made Kerala a centre of attention for its institutional and social mechanism for the marginal community.

The Government of India passed the occupational safety health and working condition code (OSH Code) in 2020 by connecting the 13 labour laws in the country. It has accurately described the safety and health standard, health and working conditions, and welfare measures. The OSH Code covers unorganized skilled and unskilled migrant workers. In structured and unstructured living places in Kerala, the hygiene system for migrant workers is not as prescribed by the rules and can be considered a failure of the local self-governing system in Kerala that implements the rules (KILE 2020). At the same time, the fact that the local self-governing system worked successfully with the health sector in the health system of migrant workers during the Covid-19 pandemic is also proof that social institutions are integrated into the health sector (Khadar 2022).

Through the National Health Mission (NHM), the Department of Health and Family Welfare introduced Link Workers in 2020 to improve access to healthcare for migrant families. In coordination with other frontline workers of the department, resourceful migrants were recruited and trained to provide health information and connect migrants to services in their own language.

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Migrant workers are among the most vulnerable groups in Kerala's health sector. Although the government is trying to involve them in the key changes coming in the health sector, the problems in effective communications health issues of hospitals, attitude of neglect by medical personals approach in the primary health sectors are among the few important issues causing concern among the migrant workers. This paper presents a study on the need to include migrant workers in healthcare sectors during the Covid era and the health policies that need to be rethought. This paper is an overview of the health sector initiatives taken to ensure the safety of vulnerable communities in Kerala.

Key Words: Labour Migration, Health Policies in Kerala, Vulnerable Community, Social and Welfare Schemes, Inclusion of Migrant Rights.

Article Methodology

Science and Engineering Research Board at Mahatma Gandhi University is conducting research from 2022 on the effect of a social institution and technological intervention on access to healthcare among interstate migrant labourers in Kerala. As part of the research, fieldwork was conducted in 53 areas in 10 districts of Kerala and conducted with interstate migrant workers, representatives of health institutions, government officials, trade union workers, NGO workers, agents among migrant workers, contractors, officials working in international organizations, representatives of local self-government bodies, and employers in various sectors. Information gathered from discussions and observations is used in this article. The necessary information has been incorporated into the articles from the reports of studies conducted among migrant workers and the examination of government documents.

Interstate Migrant Workers: Labour Process and Relevant Policy Frameworks

Recent decades a stressed increasing significant of interstate migrant workers in Kerala's employment sector to an unparalleled extent. This indicates the changing working environment with a section of workers who do not have a trade union or class-conscious ideological base as perceived by many, participate in the infrastructural and industrial developmental leap of Kerala. Coir industry, construction, food processing, stone carving, footwear industry, home furnishing, plywood industry, readymade garments, rice mill, road construction sites, metal craft, wood furniture factory, cashew factory, paper factory, rubber factory, brick industry, hotels, footwear industry, plastic industry, grass mat weaving, pottery & clay, wood turning & lacquerware, hand embroidery, cane & bamboo industry, street vendors, terracotta industry, tiles company, spices factory, tea planting and

many other industries primary sector units and service sector entities have now been largely dominated by migrant workers. Migrant workers are now employed in the above-mentioned sectors which precisely hard employed Keralites. The changes in the employment sector in Kerala that made Keralites invisible in traditional jobs, entrepreneurial jobs, service jobs, cleaning jobs and support jobs in manufacturing unit is worth examine as well as separately Migration of Keralites to Arab and the resultant important quality of life and work of Keralites are exposed to could be considered prime workers in this connection.

Estimates suggest that interstate migrant workers in Kerala are becoming the main labour force. According to the Economic Census of 2015-16, there are 3,355,004 enterprises in Kerala (MSPICSO Report 2016). According to the 2021 Kerala Planning Board Survey, the number of migrant workers in various enterprises is 34.5 lakh. Radical shift in the place of arrival of migrant workers was noted between 2001 and 2011. Most of the interstate migrant workers arriving in Kerala were from the neighbouring states of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Maharashtra as per the 2001 census. But the 2011 estimate found the largest number of migrant workers were from the states of West Bengal, Assam, Odisha, and Bihar. The 2011 census also indicates that migrant workers in Kerala are shifting from seasonal migration to residential migration processes.

Kerala has set a good example in formulating policies for inter-state migrant workers and coordinating their activities. According to the Migrant Policy Index 2019, Kerala has also secured the first rank in terms of migrant-friendly policies. But whether the policies formulated for the inter-state workers are reaching them properly should be a subject of a detailed study. In this context the right to residence, the right to participate in political processes, the right to safety of life for those engaged in hazardous work, the right to prevent exploitation of wages and sexual exploitation, the right to education, and the right to a safe health care system need to be considered and discussed extensively.

The following description tries to relate a transnational non-binding instrument on migration and discuss certain issues related to interstate migration to Kerala. The first goal of the Global Compact on Migration (a draft policy adopted by the United Nations Organization in 2018 to achieve safe, orderly, and efficient migration goals) is the importance of collecting and using evidence-based, accurate, and transparent data. Though there was an inflow of interstate migrant workers to Kerala before the 90s, it was during the 90s that the migration extended to a large scale. To date, the different governments of Kerala have not adopted a proper policy to collect and collate data on migrant workers for the last 30 years.

Goal 8 of the Global Compact on Migration calls to save lives and establish coordinated international efforts on missing migrants. Our research and filed

experience give an understanding of the current situation in Kerala shows that no specific legislation has been implemented for inter-state migrant workers in the health sector. The basic legislation formulated four decades ago is also not implemented properly. The Global Compact on Migration also discusses basic services to be provided to migrant workers. The government is yet to embark on a new policy formations that link migrant workers in Kerala to the globally accepted draft policy to which it is a signatory.

National Policy Frameworks on Interstate Migration: Recent Trends

The Government of India has introduced four labour codes to replace the existing 29 labour laws in India (Table I). These four labour codes are the wage code, industrial relations code, social security code, and personal safety and healthy working condition code. The central government underlines that the aim of the government is to ensure minimum wages, social and health security, and all the benefits of labour laws through these codes. It is in this context that the Inter-State Migrant Workers Act, of 1979 has to be examined.

Labour Codes	Included Labour Laws
1. Labour Code or Wage Code (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Payment of Wages Act, 1936; • Minimum Wages Act, 1948; • Payment of Bonus Act, 1965; • Equal Remuneration Act, 1976
1. Social Security Code (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees’ Provident Funds and Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952; • Employees’ State Insurance Act, 1948; • Employees’ Compensation Act, 1923; • Employment Exchanges (Compulsory Notification of Vacancies) Act, 1959; • Maternity Benefit Act, 1961; • Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972; • Cine-workers Welfare Fund Act, 1981; • Building and Other Construction Worker’s Welfare Cess Act, 1996; and • Unorganised Workers Social Security Act, 2008

<p>1. Occupational Safety, Health and Working Conditions Code (OSH Code 2020)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factories Act, 1948; • Mines Act, 1952; • Dock Workers (Safety, Health and Welfare) Act, 1986; • Building and Other Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996; • Plantations Labour Act, 1951; • Contract Labour (Regulation and Abolition) Act, 1970; • Inter-State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979; • Working Journalist and other Newspaper Employees (Conditions of Service and Miscellaneous Provision) Act, 1955; • Working Journalist (Fixation of Rates of Wages) Act, 1958; • Motor Transport Workers Act, 1961; • Sales Promotion Employees (Condition of Service) Act, 1976; • Beedi and Cigar Workers (Conditions of Employment) Act, 1966; and • Cine-Workers and Cinema Theatre Workers (Regulation of Employment) Act, 1981
<p>1. Industrial Relation Code (IR Code 2020)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trade Unions Act, 1926; • Industrial Employment (Standing Orders) Act, 1946, • Industrial Disputes Act, 1947

Table I: Labour Codes and Included Laws

Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) is a code for occupational safety, health, and working conditions. This code also addresses issues concerning decent working conditions, minimum wages, grievance redressal tools, protection from abuse and exploitation, improved skills, and social security for all groups of migrant workers. Kerala needs to formulate a health policy incorporating the objectives of this code for organized and unorganized workers including migrants.

Making the general health system of Kerala accessible to the migrant workers in a self-sufficient manner should be the main activity to be adopted in the health policy of the migrant workers. Kerala's health policy programs have actually evolved out of a general consensus. Social reform efforts and subsequent scientific awareness have been key drivers for growth in the health sector. According to Ministry of Health and Family Welfare data (2019), there are a total of 931 Primary Health Centres (PHC) in Kerala, including 848 Primary Health Centres in rural areas and 83 in urban areas. Kerala ranks 13th in terms of PHC activity among the states in India. The top 3 states with the highest number of PHCs are Uttar Pradesh (3560), Karnataka (2562) and Rajasthan (2459). Incidentally, Uttar Pradesh is one of the largest migrant-sending states in India. 52% of internal migration also takes place in the same state. According to the NSSO report (2008), 50% of the people are looking for employment and coming for employment in Uttar Pradesh at the same time.

The data collected by us through RTI 2005 (document No: DHS2971/2023/S2B, dated 20.02.2023) from the director of the health department the total number of PHCs in Kerala is 848. The number of PHCs is 83 less than the 2019 figures of the Government of India. If we look at the public health system, there are 6701 medical institutions in Kerala under the control of the government. PHCs have converted to family health centres (FHC) and are promoting a better system of treatment. Thus, there are currently 885 FHCs (including 41 Community Health Centres (CHC) and 844 Primary Health Centres) operating in Kerala. Out of which 156 FHCs are functioning 24X7. If the services of 6701 medical institutions are made available to migrant workers in the basic health system, there will be new developments in the health policy of migrant workers in Kerala.

Perceptions of health constantly change in trace with access to facilities the benefits of vaccination is available. 60% of the migrant workers, who shared information during the fieldwork, had received the first dose of the Covid vaccine from Kerala. There are 196 families of migrant workers living in *Etumanoor* of the Kottayam district. It was revealed to us that among them, pregnant women are receiving health-supplement pills and vaccinations are being given to babies with proper reminders. This indicates that the migrant workers are getting the basic support of Kerala's health system. But to bring this health system through a special policy for migrant workers and bring it to those who are yet to avail the benefits of the health sector are measures that the government should take.

The new policy formulations should aim to bring the state to a system where the changes are favourable to the lifeworld realities of interstate migrant workers. A discussion on whether such new policy formulation is possible in Kerala should also be initiated. Through our fieldwork, the study gave a glimpse into the larger

question on the gaps left by the studies conducted on this matter on the health sector of migrant workers. The larger question of whether migrant workers are able to address their health problems under various social security schemes and what policies have been formulated at the government level to address those problems is examined here. These are the social, health and security schemes currently in existence in Kerala for migrant workers (Table 2):

Overview

Three projects namely Interstate Migrant Welfare Scheme (IMWWS), AWAZ Health Insurance, and APNA GHAR residential project are currently being undertaken by the Kerala government. However, since 2019, the Awaz health insurance scheme has been dormant. From a conversation with 300 workers in the Kottayam district, it was revealed that only around 10 percentage workers have an Awaz insurance health card. The card is often not updated after one year of application. The work of the Special Migrant Workers Team under the District Labour Officers (DLO) for Social Health Protection of Migrant Workers has become dysfunctional and the situation is getting worse as it is not possible to find or develop the necessary facilities for registration of interstate migrant workers. Details of members of the revised health insurance scheme after 2019 are not available. Why awaz insurance card is not aware among migrant workers? Migrant workers are duped by agents who see it as a mandatory card to show up to authorities. (Raj 2023).

A study conducted by the Kerala Planning Board in 2021 reveals that 3.7 lakh migrant workers are registered under the Awaz insurance scheme. Moreover, private insurance companies are not interested in acting as insurance agencies for Awaz Insurance Scheme. The project, which was decided to be directly implemented by the government, appears to be at a standstill.

Scheme I: Interstate Migrant Workers Welfare (IMWWS)	Scheme II : AWAZ Health Insurance	Scheme III : Apna Ghar (Residential Project for Migrants Workers)
Scheme Introduced: 2010	Scheme Introduced: 2017	Scheme Introduced: 2019
Controlled Authority: Kerala Building and other construction workers Welfare board	Budget Allocation: 10 Crore*	Budget Allocation: More than 20 Crore* (3 projects)
Registrants: 58,888**	Active Cards: 5,16,320**	Beneficiaries: 1,140**

<p>Benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compensation to the ₹2 lakhs for those who enrolled and Rs family upon the death 25000 to those who not enrolled the worker • Relief benefit ₹10000 competition during membership period for temporary disability of not less than 6 months duration due to work-related accidents. • Treatment benefit ₹25000 for treatment of members for fatal diseases that requires five or more days without hospitalisation. • Terminal benefit ₹25000 to 50000 for those who exit from the labour market after a minimum of five years and enrolment under the scheme. • Body repatriation Maximum of ₹ 50000 • Education scholarships (Annual) ₹ 1000 to 3000 for migrant's children. • Maternity benefits ₹15000/- 	<p>Benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free Insurance Scheme for Interstate Migrant Workmen. • Beneficial to all migrant workmen employed within Kerala • Free medical treatment wroth ₹15,000/- per year. • Insurance Coverage of ₹2,00,000 for accident death. • Cashless medical treatment to be beneficiaries through Bio-metric cards. • Enrolment age -18 to 60 years • Any identity cards recognised by the central / state government should be produced at the time of registration. • Treatment is available from all government hospitals as well as from empanelled private hospitals. • Facilitation entre opened from all districts. 	<p>Benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Government of Kerala to provide safe and hygienic accommodation. • Dormitory available for rent (₹1000/ Month) to migrant workers • <i>Kanjikkod</i> (Palakkad) and <i>Kinaloor</i> (Kozhikode) projects have been completed. • Land acquisition for the project has started in <i>Kalamassery</i> (Ernakulam).
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Table 2: Social, health and security schemes in Kerala.

Source: Labour Commissionerate website, Awaz Insurance website, Government Documents

*The Hindu Report -2015

** Recorded from the government site.

Based on detailed interaction with Adv. Binu Bose, State office bearer of All Kerala Migrant Workers Union, it was understood that the Interstate Migrant

Workers Welfare Scheme is very well advanced. A specially designed application -*Guest App*, registers the construction workers in the scheme by entering their details as per their Aadhaar card. Mr. Bose opines that the migrant workers who come to Kerala, start working in the construction sector, which has been marked by the International Labour Organization as the most hazardous work sector. Our fieldwork reveals that the respective contractors/employers are not trying to fully deliver the facilities the Construction and Welfare Board offers to the migrant workers.

In this unique situation of Kerala, it is necessary to find a new approach based on rights for migrant workers according to international laws and the information available thus far from Indian laws and policies. Governments are already aware of the need to legislate on the health issues of migrant workers. The poor living conditions of the migrant workers, the crisis they face if they get sick, and their unwillingness to voice issues they face is caused by the government's inaction.

What should be the health policy for migrant workers?

Infectious diseases, chemical and pesticide-related diseases, skin diseases, heat stress, respiratory conditions, musculoskeletal disorders, and traumatic injuries are common problems that migrant workers may experience during work. Unhygienic living conditions lead to chronic infections and other communicable diseases. Migrant workers working in quarries suffer from respiratory diseases such as silicosis and tuberculosis (TB) (Borhade 2011).

Lack of knowledge and awareness on healthcare from the stakeholders is the main problem faced by the migrants. The unavailability of social institutions or technological interfaces to help them understand existing health services also points to the need for policy formulation. In most cases, migrant workers have to travel long distances from their homes after working hours, which takes up most of their time. Therefore, they are unable to access the health system. A lack of familiarity with online applications was also revealed during our fieldwork.

Basic facilities such as drinking water, toilets, etc. provided to migrant workers are unsanitary and limited. They are unaware of the legal systems that can help them get better living conditions. They get marginalized from all kinds of legal systems as mandated by the migration Act of 1979. Life in open spaces and cramped cabins makes them more susceptible to diseases.

At present, judging by the social situation in Kerala, women migrant workers are coming on a large scale. Women at first accompanied their husbands and found jobs here. But now women are coming alone in search of jobs. Health problems faced by women can be considered fraught with danger. Maternal health issues

(including sexual and reproductive health) and lack of awareness, knowledge, and skills to make rational choices and use the services of social health institutions are limited among women migrant workers (Borhade 2016).

Although traditional healthcare systems, access systems, and disease prevention facilities exist in Kerala, services from modern healthcare providers are particularly difficult for migrant women. Health care, including maternal, appears to be isolated. The reasons why women migrant workers are going to their native places for childbirth should be discussed.

Changes to be incorporated in health policy formulation

Based on different regulations given by various organizations, information obtained from discussions with various academic thinkers, and social activists, and personal experience from fieldwork the following recommendations, suggestions and comments are made. Understanding the importance given to the life and health of migrant workers in various resolutions of the United Nations and the International Labour Organization, fundamental changes should be made through the formulation of a new law for migrant workers. DPSP, Article 23 (1), Article 39, Article 42, and Article 43 of the Constitution of India shall be legislated for all workers including migrant workers (See table 3).

Standards Governing Migration Policy
<i>International – Law and Rights</i>
<p>Follow the UDHR¹ Article I: All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood</p> <p>And</p> <p>Article II: “Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.”</p> <p>“Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.”</p>
<p>Follow the IHRL² Obligations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Respect – Refraining from arbitrary detention, torture, or collective expulsion of migrants. 2. Protect - Regulate recruitment agencies, sanction abusive employers, protect migrants from violence and abuse by smugglers, and take action against xenophobia and hatred. 3. Fulfil - Introducing alternatives to detention, and guaranteeing access to healthcare, education, and other social services.

<p>Follow the Human Rights Principle:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Equality and Non-Discrimination 2. Participation and Inclusion 3. Accountability and Rule of Law
<p>Review the report on the compendium of principles good practices and policies on, safe orderly and safe migration in line with the international human rights law³.</p>
<p>Refer to the International Labour Standards on the Labour Migration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ILO⁴ Instruments –Conventions
<p>To study the GCM⁵ 23 Objectives and manage interstate migration at different levels</p>
<p><i>National – Constitutional Law and Rights</i></p>
<p>Article 23 (1): Traffic in human beings and beggar and other similar forms of forced labour are prohibited and any contravention of this provision shall be an offence punishable in accordance with law</p>
<p>Article 39: Certain principles of policy to be followed by the State: The State shall, in particular, direct its policy towards securing</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. <i>that the citizens, men and women equally, have the right to an adequate means to livelihood;</i> ii. <i>that the ownership and control of the material resources of the community are so distributed as best to subserve the common good;</i> iii. <i>that the operation of the economic system does not result in the concentration of wealth and means of production to the common detriment;</i> iv. <i>that there is equal pay for equal work for both men and women;</i> v. <i>that the health and strength of workers, men and women, and the tender age of children are not abused and that citizens are not forced by economic necessity to enter avocations unsuited to their age or strength;</i> vi. <i>that children are given opportunities and facilities to develop in a healthy manner and in conditions of freedom and dignity and that childhood and youth are protected against exploitation and against moral and material abandonment</i>
<p>Article 42: Provision for just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief The State shall make provision for securing just and humane conditions of work and for maternity relief.</p>
<p>Article 43: Living wage, etc, for workers the State shall endeavour to secure, by suitable legislation or economic organisation or in any other way, to all workers, agricultural, industrial or otherwise, work, a living wage, conditions of work ensuring a decent standard of life and full enjoyment of leisure and social and cultural opportunities and, in particular, the State shall endeavour to promote cottage industries on an individual or co-operative basis in rural areas.</p>

Table 3 : International and National Laws and Rights.

- Sources:
1. Website of United Nation Human Rights Office of the High Commissioner, UDHR, Indian Constitution, ILO.
 2. Universal Declaration of Human Rights.
 3. International Human Rights Law
 4. Human Rights Council Thirty-Sixth Session Report -A/HRC/36/42.
 5. International Labour Organisation
 6. Global Compact for (Safe, Orderly and Regular) Migration

General Observations

Insurance schemes like Awaz Insurance are meant to be made available to migrant workers and require the services of senior officials like district labour officers, but these officers are not always accessible to migrant workers. Hence governments should be cautious in appointing special officers for migrant workers in district jurisdictions.

In 2010, Kerala Government changed Interstate Migrant Workers Welfare Scheme into Awaaz Insurance Scheme and the Government withdrew from the welfare scheme activities. A new law should be enacted which includes the rights guaranteed by Indian laws and the Constitution, which are in line with the international law.

The new policy plans should incorporate those adopted by India in resolutions emphasizing the welfare and safety of workers upholding international human rights

Recommendation

1. An 'accident grant scheme' should be announced for workers aged 18 to 65 years on the model of the "*Bihar State Migrant Mazdoor Accident Grant Scheme*" Act for migrant workers in Bihar. There are many health insurances available with very low premiums that can be paid annually. Similarly, a special accident grand scheme should be provided only to Migrant workers.
2. A new scheme for special care of women and children should be announced for migrant workers only. A special grant should be allocated for data collection of migrant workers in the home contact program conducted by Asha workers in Kerala. Extra attention should be given for pre and post natal healthcare.
3. The government should allocate a special fund for the health and social security of the migrant workers to the local self-governing bodies and appoint an officer there to deal with issues related to migrant workers.
4. A special call centre should be established for addressing queries of migrant workers, made available in different languages, making policies more accessible.
5. Similar to the Asha workers in Kerala, migrant women labourers should be employed in primary health centres to increase the interaction between the authorities and migrant labourers.

6. Collaborate with other states to negotiate at the government level for deputation services of representatives from home states for migrant workers. The Kerala Government should make use of the contract recruitment system to employ those nominated from other states on a trial basis in areas where labour mobilization is high.
7. Public relations department's advertisements on social security, health care and labour laws should also be published in the mother tongue of migrant workers.
8. The Kerala government should initiate basic orientation for the worker's program in their language of choice. The migrant works arriving are not proficient in the local language and causes inaccessibility of existing policies. This language barrier should be given special attention.

Suggestions

1. Government policies must be developed that include the classification of 29 laws, including the Inter-State Migration Act, into four labour codes
2. To ratify and articulate the Global Compact on Migration, discussions should be held for the formulation of national legal policies.
3. Policy approaches should be adopted to change the social institutions in such a way that the migrant workers can rely on them quickly and do not face language barriers.
4. Other laws existing in India should be brought under one umbrella and regulated separately in the legislation for migrant workers.
5. In order to create awareness about the increasing incidence of sexually transmitted diseases and AIDS among migrant workers, it is necessary to recruit from among them and employ them on a contract basis to spread awareness.

Conclusion

Even though there are schemes existing to ensure the welfare of migrant labourers, in reality, investigational fieldwork revealed that there was a lack of understanding of how to run the schemes implemented by the government. Since Kerala has a huge inflow of migrant labourers, it is important to formulate new healthcare policies that help these migrant labourers. Lack of actual data is also a problem in implementing existing policies. However, an effort to estimate workers' strength according to the major occupational category through a system of accounting to include employers, LSGs, labour department, Akshaya centre and

institutional workers operating at grass root level may be initiated to impact radical change in the estimated system.

It is the responsibility of the government to provide clear information about their working conditions and living conditions to the migrant workers arriving in Kerala. To fulfil such responsibilities, a special team should be appointed under District Labour Officers across Kerala to provide them with a clear understanding of registration, health care and lifestyle of migrant workers. The Kerala government should also adopt procedures to make migrant workers beneficiaries of health systems in Kerala.

The social health and safety schemes currently being implemented in Kerala need to continue. Such as the Awaz Insurance Scheme is currently dysfunctional. Efforts to mobilize them further and make more workers members of the scheme should also be done in the government's Labour, Health, and Education system.

Beyond the above-mentioned directives, the government should urgently intervene in policy formulation for migrant workers by incorporating expert advice from those working in the sector. Due to this, Kerala's current activities in the welfare of migrant workers will get more recognition than other states. It is possible to create a positive healthcare system in our state only if we protect the inter-state workers who are crucial in Kerala's workforce.

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Book

Jalan, Bimal (1991): *India's Economic Crisis*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Article or Chapter in an edited Volume/Book

Thomas, A. M. (2005): "India and Southeast Asia: The Look East Policy in Perspective," in Rajan Harshe and K.M. Seethi (eds.), *Engaging with the World: Critical Reflections on India's Foreign Policy*, New Delhi: Orient Longman.

Website:

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FORM IV

Statement about ownership and other particulars of the Indian Journal of Politics and International Relations under Rule 8 of the Registration of Newspapers (Central), Rules, 1956.

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1. Place of Publication | School of International Relations and Politics (SIRP)
Mahatma Gandhi University,
Priyadarshini Hills P.O.,
Kottayam, Kerala, India-686560 |
| 2. Periodicity of Publication | Bi-annual |
| 3. Printer's Name
Nationality
Address | C. Vinodan
Indian
Director, SIRP,
Mahatma Gandhi University,
Priyadarshini Hills P.O.,
Kottayam, Kerala, India-686560 |
| 4. Publisher's Name
Nationality
Address | C. Vinodan
Indian
Director, SIRP,
Mahatma Gandhi University,
Priyadarshini Hills P.O.,
Kottayam, Kerala, India-686560 |
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@ Registrar, Mahatma Gandhi University 2023 Vol. 16 No. 1

ISSN 0973-5011

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ISSN 0973-3041